

We used the multiple linear regression technique to generate an equation to serve as an empirical model to predict rice leaf blast on cultivar RD23. This model can be used as part of a blast management program in Thailand. The equation is based on leaf blast severity as the dependent variable assessed 32 d after sowing (DAS) from weekly sowings of the cultivar in 1993-94 under dry (upland) conditions at Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi. Plants were grown and maintained in 1-m² plots. Ammonium phosphate fertilizer (16-20-0) was applied to the plots along with 100 kg N ha⁻¹.

For each category of leaf blast severity assessed, the likelihood of that severity correlating with a weather variable (e.g., rainfall frequency, number of days with relative humidity \geq 80%, mean maximum temperature) was estimated using WINDOW PANE, a weather variable searching computer program available at IRRI. This software served as an intercessory tool in developing the empirical model to better identify weather variables with direct effects on blast. The searching mechanism of WINDOW PANE is based on a series of time durations during which a particular weather variable occurs. For each time duration, correlation with leaf blast severity was estimated. Weather variables occurring at certain time durations that WINDOW PANE found to have high correlation with leaf blast severities were then chosen as independent variables in regression analysis.

A best fitting equation was based on the following selection criteria: high adjusted coefficient of determination (r^2), coefficient of variation (CV) < 25%, low predicted error sum of squares (PRESS), predictors with variance inflation factors (VIF) < 10, and regression coefficients (β 's) with significance level (P) \leq 0.05.

The best fitting equation used as an empirical model to predict percent leaf blast severity (Y) on RD23 is

$$Y = [56.184 - 8.261 \sqrt{\text{MMAX}} - 0.710(\text{MWS}^3)]^2$$

where MMAX is the mean maximum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at time durations from 40 d before sowing (DBS) to 14 DAS, and MWS is the mean windspeed from 40 DBS to 24 DAS. The equation has r^2 , CV, and PRESS values of 0.87, 11.62, and 23.86, respectively. All independent variables

Comparison of observed and predicted leaf blast severities observed 32 d after sowing on RD23. Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi, Thailand.^a

Statistical parameter	Fitting sample (n = 20)	Validation sample (n = 6)
r	0.914**	0.955**
β_0	-2.146 ^{ns}	5.579 ^{ns}
β_1	1.044**	0.829**
f	0.096 ^{ns}	1.587 ^{ns}
t_{pooled}	0.072 ^{ns}	0.375 ^{ns}

^aValues followed by ** and ns are significant ($P \leq 0.05$) and not significant ($P > 0.05$), respectively; n = number of observations.

Risk prediction chart for leaf blast on RD23 sown at Uthong Field Crop Experiment Station, Suphanburi, Thailand, during 1993-1994. Infection: N = no infection; L = light (severity: 1-25%); M = moderate (severity: 27-66%); S = severe (severity: 67-100%).

have VIF values < 10 and their coefficients (β 's) have $P \leq 0.05$, which suggested uncorrelated independent variables that are important in the model.

The above equation was validated by comparing the actual and predicted severities for both fitting and validation samples (see table). The equation is useful in predicting leaf blast if the correlation coefficient (r) is > 0.85 ; the intercept (β_0) and slope parameters (β_1) have $P > 0.05$ and $P > 0.05$, respectively; and the f [modified F statistic that tests simultaneously β_0 and β_1 to be not different from zero ($P > 0.05$) and unity (≤ 0.05), respectively] and pooled t -statistic (t_{pooled}) values have $P > 0.05$ in the validation sample. We found the equation

satisfied these criteria reasonably well (see table) for both samples.

A risk prediction chart for leaf blast in Suphanburi (see figure) was developed based on the predictions of the empirical model using different values of MMAX and MWS. From the chart, moderate to high blast risk exists at MMAX of 30-38 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and MWS of 0-2.0 ms^{-1} and a disease management intervention, such as fungicide application, may be needed. The chart also suggests that during days with 3.0 m s^{-1} windspeed, interventions would be unnecessary regardless of MMAX level, as blast would not substantially reduce rice yield. ■

Use of lesion number per leaf area to estimate lesion size for leaf blast quantitative studies

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Leaf blast quantitative resistance studies to determine quantitative trait loci routinely use the parameters lesion number leaf area⁻¹ (LnA) and lesion size leaf area⁻¹ (LsA). Counting the number of sporulating lesions and measuring size using standard assessment keys make disease assessment prohibitively labor-intensive if samples are large.

A high correlation between LnA and LsA has been reported in several studies. Lesion number is easily derived by simple counts, while lesion area is probably the most biologically significant. Therefore, we propose a mathematical model to describe their relationship, estimating LsA based on LnA alone.

Data sets from two leaf blast polycyclic experiments done in the greenhouse using F₇-recombinant inbred lines (RILs) of CO 39/IAC 165 and doubled haploid (DH) lines from IR64/Azucena, including their parent cultivars, were analyzed. Replications 3 and 4 were done on a staggered basis, with each replicate separated by 2 wk. LnA and LsA data were taken 2 wk after the plants were spray-inoculated with blast spore suspension. Isolates CA42 and PO6-6 were used to infect the RILs and DH lines, respectively. A total of 1318 disease observations were generated from the inoculation work. Out of this number, 988

observations were used to develop the model for LsA. The remaining 330 observations were used to validate the generated model.

Multiple regression analysis indicated a significant exponential relationship between LnA and LsA (Fig. 1). This relationship is described in the mathematical model as

$$LsA = \exp(1.545387 + 0.900306 (\ln LnA))$$

where LsA is lesion size in $\text{mm}^2 \text{cm}^{-2}$ leaf area, \ln is the natural logarithm with base e ($e = 2.718$), and LnA is lesion number cm^{-2} leaf area. The model fits the disease observations reasonably well with a coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.85. Both the β_0 (y-intercept) and β_1 (slope coefficient) coefficient terms have significant contributions to the model with t-values of 105.4 and 86.7, respectively. To test the validity of the model, the closeness in the values of LsA in the validation set and that of the model-predicted LsA was determined.

Three criteria were used to determine such closeness: the variance (VAR_{diff}) of the difference between observed and predicted values (prediction error) is less than the mean square error (MSE) from the regression analysis of the full data set ($n=1,318$), average prediction error (APE)

1. Relationship between lesion number and lesion size in leaf blast.

is close to zero, and the β_0 and β_1 obtained from regressing actual and predicted LsA is not significantly different from zero and unity, respectively.

A 1:1 relationship between observed and predicted LsA for the validation data set ($n = 330$) was revealed (Fig. 2). The VAR_{diff} (0.2704) was less than the MSE (0.2856) of the full data set and the APE was 0.0025, which is near zero value. Likewise, both β_0 and β_1 terms satisfy the third criterion,

2. Linear relationship of predicted and observed lesion size.

suggesting that the model presented could be used to accurately estimate the LsA on the basis of LnA from new blast data sets. These data sets would likely come from various blast studies, specifically cultivar resistance screening, compatibility and virulence spectrum studies, and validation experiments for simulation models.

These results apply to sporulating blast lesions. ■

A simple method for estimating yield loss of rice due to severe panicle blast

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We investigated the relationship between panicle blast severity and yield loss of rice. We showed that yield loss can be estimated using a simple method under severe panicle blast situations.

We used Mineasahi, a Japanese rice cultivar with a low level of partial resistance to blast, and near-isogenic lines (NILs) with different complete resistance genes to blast. These NILs were developed from Japanese rice cultivars Sasanishiki and Nipponbare.

Seedlings were transplanted at 15- × 30-cm spacing in 5.8- m^2 plots during 1992-94.

Blast developed in the plots from natural infection. To obtain different levels of panicle blast severity, several fungicides were applied to Mineasahi, and mixed or

single plantings of NILs with different resistances to blast were made. Panicle blast severity was assessed by the Asaga scale (see table) on 20 representative hills in each plot about 1 mo after heading. The mean of the assessed values was transformed to a

Asaga scale for assessing panicle blast severity in ricefields.

Grade	Description	Diseased spikelets ^a (%)
0	No panicle blast observed.	0
1	A few panicle branches diseased (slight). Diseased panicle branches are seen at a glance and neck blast is found in some cases (moderate).	5 10
3	Many panicle branches are diseased and neck blast is observed (a lot).	25
4	Many panicle branches are diseased and diseased neck nodes are moderate (severe).	50
5	Panicle branches and neck nodes are severely diseased (very severe).	75
6	All panicles are diseased.	100

^aDiseased spikelets include the spikelets prematurely killed by infection of *P. grisea* on neck nodes, panicle branches, and spikelet pedicels.